

STUDIES ON LIPASE FROM OIL SEEDS. PART X. SYNTHESIS OF SOME ESTERS BY RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEED

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Synthesis of some aliphatic esters by ricinus lipase from castor seed have been carried out in order to study the effect of the nature of the alcoholic group on the enzymic synthesis of esters.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 261) studied in detail the enzymic synthesis of different propionates and butyrates and found that the maximum percentage synthesis increased from methyl to amyl ester.

The synthesis of the following esters was carried out using acetone-dried lipase in ether solvent in order to study the effect of the nature of the alcoholic group (the structure of the alcohol) on the synthesis of *n*-, *sec*- and *tert*- butyl and amyl esters of propionic and butyric acids by lipase.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were :

1. *n*-Butyl alcohol, b.p. 118°; *d* 0.809 g./c.c.
2. *sec*- Butyl alcohol, b.p. 99.5°; *d* 0.808
3. *tert*- Butyl alcohol, b.p. 82.9°; *d* 0.779
4. *n*- Amyl alcohol, b.p. 130°; *d* 0.814
5. *sec*- Amyl alcohol, b.p. 118.5°; *d* 0.810
6. *tert*- Amyl alcohol, b.p. 102°; *d* 0.809
7. Propionic acid, b.p. 141°; *d* 0.992
8. Butyric acid, b.p. 163°; *d* 0.958

In each flask, equimolecular quantities (0.054 g./mol.) of alcohol and acid, 1 g. of lipase in 10 c.c. of ether solvent and a few drops of toluene were taken and incubated at 37°. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. of it was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. Always a blank accompanied the sample. From the difference in readings, the percentage synthesis was calculated. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Percentage synthesis on the

Esters	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
<i>n</i> -Butyl propionate	12.5	15.6	21.7	26.2	28.4	29.2
<i>sec</i> - " "	20.3	27.5	32.3	38.9	42.5	41.4
<i>tert</i> - " "	31.0	37.2	43.5	50.1	55.6	57.8
<i>n</i> -Butyl butyrate	11.2	13.3	14.8	20.5	24.5	28.3
<i>sec</i> - " "	21.1	25.2	29.5	35.2	39.8	40.2
<i>tert</i> - " "	31.2	36.7	41.7	47.6	52.1	55.3

TABLE I (contd.)

Esters.	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
<i>n</i> -Amyl propionate	45.1	55.7	71.2	77.2	76.8	—
<i>sec.</i> - "	53.1	65.6	81.3	79.8	—	—
<i>tert.</i> - "	58.3	70.5	74.8	83.8	—	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl butyrate	30.8	55.0	64.9	69.3	78.1	—
<i>sec.</i> - "	42.3	64.8	79.2	81.7	84.5	—
<i>tert.</i> - "	52.3	72.4	76.3	84.6	83.8	—

From the table it is found that in case of butyl as well as amyl esters of propionic and butyric acids, the percentage of synthesis increases in the order : normal, secondary and tertiary alcoholic ester. There is a marked difference among primary, secondary and tertiary esters in which the structures of the alcohols are different which will help us to differentiate between primary, secondary and tertiary esters. It can also be seen in each case that the percentage synthesis depends only on the nature of the alcohol and not on the number of carbon atoms in the acid, as the percentage synthesis only changes with the nature of the alcohol, and the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol remains almost the same with the change in the number of carbon atoms in the acid.

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Received November 7, 1950.

STUDIES ON LIPASE FROM OIL SEEDS. PART XI. EFFECT OF H-ION CONCENTRATION AND THE NATURE OF THE BUFFER ON THE SYNTHESIS OF AMYL BUTYRATE BY RICINUS LIPASE FROM CASTOR SEED

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Synthesis of amyl butyrate by ricinus lipase has been carried out using different buffer solutions of varying p_{H} in order to study the effect of H-ion concentration and the nature of the buffer on the enzymic synthesis of esters.

Ramakrishnan and Nevgi (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 261) studied in detail the synthesis of different aliphatic esters belonging to a homologous series using acetone-dried lipase from castor seed and ether as a solvent and the maximum percentage synthesis of 78.1% was observed in case of *n*-amyl butyrate on the fifth day.

The effect of H-ion concentration and the nature of the buffer on the enzymic synthesis of *n*-amyl butyrate have been studied in the present investigation using different buffer solutions of varying p_H .

EXPERIMENTAL

The acetone-dried sample of the lipase was prepared from fresh, well ripened castor seeds by Ramakrishnan and Nevgi's method (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1950, "Science Issue") and used for the experiment. Disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer mixtures of different p_H were prepared according to McIlvaine's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 49, 183) and sodium acetate-HCl and sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer mixtures of different p_H according to Walpoles method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 108, 2501, 2521).

The synthesis of amyl butyrate by acetone-dried lipase was carried out at different p_H using different buffer mixtures.

Each set of experiments consisted of *n*-amyl alcohol (0.054 g. mol.) [(CH₂)₅CH₂OH, *d* 0.814 g./c.c. M.W. 88.15; b.p.=130°], butyric acid (0.054 g. mol.) [CH₃CH₂CH₂COOH; *d* 0.958 g./c.c. M.W. 88; b.p.=163°], lipase (1 g.), ether solvent (10 c.c.) and 5 c.c. of buffer of varying p_H value and a few drops of toluene taken in a conical flask. The flask was corked and shaken well and incubated at 37°. Always a blank accompanied each sample. Necessary precautions were taken to note readings under sterile conditions. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion from each flask was taken, 25 c.c. of neutral alcohol added, warmed for some time and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. From the difference in readings between the sample and the blank, the percentage synthesis was calculated. The results are given in the following tables.

TABLE I

Optimum p_H using disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer.

p_H	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
2.4	15.7	22.9	27.8	37.8	52.3	47.8
2.8	18.6	27.8	31.9	42.9	57.8	50.9
3.1	22.1	30.6	38.2	50.1	62.1	57.8
4.8	25.6	35.2	40.1	58.6	69.7	62.1
5.2	30.8	40.5	45.8	62.4	80.2	69.5
5.5	27.8	37.9	42.8	53.8	69.6	52.1
5.7	25.3	32.8	39.6	48.6	59.0	48.7
6.2	22.9	29.6	35.6	39.5	48.2	42.5

TABLE II

Optimum p_H using sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer.

p _H .	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
1.5	7.5	13.8	18.9	22.1	29.5	27.6
2.9	8.9	15.2	22.1	28.5	32.8	30.1
3.8	10.1	17.5	25.6	30.7	37.5	35.6
4.3	12.3	21.3	29.8	34.9	41.9	39.8
4.8	15.3	25.2	32.5	38.6	45.2	44.3
5.2	20.5	30.1	38.2	45.9	58.6	55.5
5.5	18.2	25.6	30.0	40.8	51.6	53.3
5.7	15.2	23.4	25.6	35.8	45.9	42.3
6.0	12.8	20.6	21.8	31.9	36.8	33.9

TABLE III

Optimum p_H using sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer.

p _H .	Percentage synthesis on the					
	1st day.	2nd day.	3rd day.	4th day.	5th day.	6th day.
3.8	7.6	8.2	11.9	17.5	24.8	21.6
4.1	8.0	9.5	13.8	18.9	27.5	23.4
4.8	9.5	11.1	15.2	21.8	29.8	25.6
4.9	10.1	12.8	18.1	25.3	32.6	30.1
5.5	10.8	15.2	20.9	30.2	41.3	38.4
5.7	9.2	14.1	19.5	25.2	35.6	32.8
5.9	8.5	12.9	17.2	22.8	32.3	30.9
6.0	7.9	9.8	15.6	19.1	29.6	27.5

DISCUSSION

From the above tables, it is found that the optimum p_H for enzymic synthesis of amyl butyrate is 5.2 in case of disodium phosphate-citric acid and sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid buffer and 5.5 in case of sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. It can be seen that the optimum p for the synthesis of ester by ricinus lipase slightly varies (5.2 to 5.5) with the nature of the buffer used. But at the same time, the maximum percentage synthesis reached is the greatest in case of disodium phosphate-citric acid buffer and the least in sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. Generally in all cases, the percentage synthesis reaches the maximum on the 5th day.

Thus, it is inferred that the enzymic synthesis of ester depends upon the H-ion concentration, the nature of the buffer used and the time of reaction.

Further work is under progress to study the effect of the buffer concentration and enzyme concentration on the synthesis of esters by lipase.